

Quasi-Independent Voltage-Reactive Power Zone Controller

Jasna Dragosavac

Žarko Janda

Automation&Control

Electrical Engineering Institute Nikola Tesla

Belgrade, Serbia

jasna.dragosavac@ieent.org

Jovica V. Milanović

School of Electrical and Electronic Engineering

The University of Manchester

Manchester, UK

jovica.milanovic@manchester.ac.uk

Abstract—In this paper the zone controller is presented which regulates the reactive power-voltage characteristic (Q-V) of the zone pilot node by altering the reactive power outputs of power plants within the zone. As far as the zone is self-sufficient regarding reactive power needs, the generation is adapted to fit consumption and quasi-independent operation is achieved. As soon as limits are reached the import/export of the zone has to be permitted and voltage is maintained along the defined Q-V characteristics while providing reactive support to surrounding zones. Reactive power is distributed among power plants according to equal reactive reserve margin so maximal voltage stability margin is maintained. The result is minimization of losses due to minimization of reactive power flows among the zones and thus across long distances. Finally simulation results of the proposed controller are given in order to present the controller response in the quasi-independent operation mode.

Index Terms—Reactive power voltage control, Pilot node, Zone controller

I. INTRODUCTION

In France [1] and Italy [2] secondary voltage control in power grid has been established in late 80s and upgraded in 90s [3] in order to optimize voltage control of power grid with enhancement of security of operation and lowering of losses which occur in the transmission system. However with changes caused by deregulation of energy market and involvement of renewables there is a space for some modifications and improvements. Requirements for power plant connections to grid nowadays recognize power plant as a whole rather than single unit within a power plant, due to renewables which often consist of large number of small units [4]. On the other side the market demand to connect different market participants resulted in the very meshed networks at all levels (distribution, LV, MV, HV transmission). Maintaining desirable voltage profiles which minimizes transmission losses, with large number of generators and superimposed market demands for power transfers, becomes a challenge. Regarding voltages, the power system is naturally divided into voltage control zones, Fig 1. Single zone incorporates all the plants whose reactive power output affects the voltage of selected zone's most respective node, the pilot node (PN). The

zones are chosen to be self-sufficient regarding reactive power needs so reactive power transfers to neighbouring zones is minimal. The losses connected to reactive power flows across transmission lines and long distances are thus minimized. If each zone is equipped with "zone" controller, the voltages across the power system could be controlled by mean of zone controllers coordination. The device called CQVC (coordinated reactive power-voltage controller), [3], unifies all the generators in the one power plant in single equivalent generator regarding reactive power-voltage characteristics at the point of common coupling. The idea is, at zone level, to unify all the CQVCs of the power plants in the zone into single equivalent reactive power-voltage controller of the zone called "zone" controller. In Italy plant controllers have been in use for some time now [2] and in Serbia since few years ago [3]. In France zone controllers, which are coordinated by secondary voltage control of power system, changes directly the reference voltage value of the automatic voltage regulators at all the generators in the certain zone.

Figure 1. Zoning of power system in Serbia

Figure 2. Zone voltage controller characteristic (change in sum of generated reactive powers at power plants ΣQ_{PPn} as a function of sum of Q_{ij} reactive power inflows at boundary lines) within V_{PN_low} to V_{PN_high} region

Figure 3. Block diagram of the zone voltage controller within V_{PN_low} to V_{PN_high} range:

- AVG - the averaging block contains resettable integrator with operating reset time interval T_I
- PI_1 - the discrete Proportional-integral (PI) controller
- V_{PN_target} - the pilot node target voltage value; it is transferred into each CQVC (involved into zone voltage control) voltage reference change to keep uniform reactive power margins at all plants

Figure 4. Pilot node Q-V characteristic, pilot node voltage is given as a function of total zone reactive power

In this paper the zone controller is presented. The first step could be to control smaller parts of the power system, zones, as quasi-independent entities, Fig. 1. Due to electricity market demands a reactive power requirements have to be fulfilled in real time in order to maintain voltage profile across power network. Under these control requirements the distributed control approach is more robust than the centralized one due to handling with local informations. The first aim of zone controller is to balance reactive power consumption and generation within a zone, Fig. 2 and Fig. 3. Different power sources with different time responses are connected within the same voltage zone. The voltage zone is self-sufficient in reactive power until the zone PN voltage remains approximately equal to arithmetic mean value of the surrounding zones voltages. While the voltage zone is self-sufficient in reactive power, the net output zone reactive power flow is close to zero. Therefore the regulation objective in this operating state is to maintain zero exchange reactive power, while the zone pilot node voltage is dictated by surrounding voltage zones. The corresponding voltage interval is between V_{PN_low} and V_{PN_high} , Fig. 4. When this voltage interval is exceeded, the regulation mode changes to voltage control with zone output reactive power droop. When zone's pilot node voltage approaches its' absolute limit values, the pilot node voltage is controlled according to the predefined reactive power-voltage (Q-V) characteristic with defined droop, Fig. 4. At this point, some amount of reactive power is imported/exported from the neighbouring zones. In such way the reactive support of surrounding voltage zones is realized as strong as possible under reactive constrains. Eventually, when zone's reactive capabilities become exhausted, the pilot node voltage would not be able to be maintained by reactive resources within the zone any more.

II. ZONE CONTROLLER

In this paper the concept of independent zone controller is discussed. This controller changes the reference voltage value of power plant coordinated reactive power – voltage controller (CQVC) and controls the shunt reactors and capacitors banks in order to minimize the net reactive power flow through interconnection lines of the zones, the first operating mode, Fig. 4, purple line. When voltage of the pilot node approaches the predefined high, V_{pp_high} and low, V_{pp_low} , values the reactors/capacitors are manipulated. In this way, dynamic reactive reserve, available at synchronous generators, is preserved, Fig. 2. When voltages cross the V_{pp_high} and low, V_{pp_low} , values the pilot node Q-V characteristic is maintained with certain droop, the second operating mode, Fig.4, green line. The net inflow of reactive power is permitted in order to keep voltage control capability of the zone. At this point there exists an unbalance of generation and consumption of reactive power within the zone. The Q-V characteristic is maintained until the zone reactive capacity is exhausted.

While pilot node voltage (V_{PN}) is within acceptable range (1) the generated reactive power in the power plants should equal consumption and sum of reactive power inflows in the zone should be corrected (2).

$$V_{PN_low} < V_{PN} < V_{PN_high} \quad (1)$$

where V_{PN} pilot node voltage, V_{PN_low} critically acceptable low value of pilot node voltage, V_{PN_high} critically acceptable high value of pilot node voltage ,

$$\Delta \sum_n Q_{PPn} = \sum_j Q_{ij} \quad (2)$$

Q_{PPn} generated reactive power at power plant n ,
 Q_{ij} reactive power flow at line between nodes i and j ,

Assuming that the entire voltage zone is properly presented by pilot node voltage, the voltage control, which ensures that objective given by (2) is achieved within V_{PN_low} to V_{PN_high} range, is shown in Fig. 2.

When approaching critically permitted values of pilot node voltage (3) the import/export of the zone reactive power has to be permitted and voltage could only be maintained along the defined Q-V characteristics, Fig. 2.

$$V_{PN} > V_{PN_high} \text{ or } V_{PN} < V_{PN_low} \quad (3)$$

To maintain the voltage at pre-disturbance pilot node Q-V characteristic, the zone controller should change reactive power in the zone Q_{zone_i} to reach point 3 in Fig. 4. The zone controller therefore calculates $Q_{zone_i_new}$ for the desired pilot node reference value V_{PNref} and pilot node Q-V characteristic droop value $X_{droopPN}$ and estimated network reactance X_{net} and enters it into reactive power controller as:

$$Q_{zone_i_new} = \frac{Q_{zone_i} + \frac{V_{PNref} - V_{PN}}{X_{net}}}{1 + \frac{X_{droopPN}}{X_{net}}} \quad (4)$$

where

$$Q_{zone_i} = \sum_n Q_{PPn} - Q_{zone_load} = \sum_j Q_{ij} \quad (5)$$

where Q_{zone_i} is the reactive power in the zone i , Q_{zone_load} is the total reactive load of the zone i , and V_{PN} is the pre-disturbance voltage

The droop value $X_{droopPN}$ is chosen in a way to achieve the low voltage limit of 0.95 and ΣQ_{PPmax} simultaneously, taking into account values recommended by ENTSOe [4].

The new value of total generated power within the zone is

$$\sum_n Q_{PPn_new} = Q_{zone_i_new} - Q_{zone_load} \quad (6)$$

Reactive power is distributed among power plants according equal reactive reserve margin [3]

$$k_{zone_i} = \frac{\sum_n Q_{PPn_new} - \sum_n Q_{PPn_min}}{\sum_n Q_{PPn_max} - \sum_n Q_{PPn_min}} \quad (7)$$

where

k_{zone_i} loading coefficient of the zone

$\Sigma Q_{PPn_min/max}$ sum maximum/minimum available reactive power at power plants in the zone

Generated reactive power at power plant n is

$$Q_{PPn_new} = k_{zone_i} (Q_{PPn_max} - Q_{PPn_min}) \quad (8)$$

$Q_{PPn_min/max}$ maximum/minimum available reactive power at power plant n

Change of reactive power at plant n ΔQ_{PPn}

$$\Delta Q_{PPn} = Q_{PPn_new} - Q_{PPn} \quad (9)$$

This change in the reactive power of the power plant should be transformed in adequate change of voltage reference value of plant controller CQVC. The reference voltage value change at power plant controller CQVC should be

$$[\Delta |V_{PPn}|] = [S]^{-1} \left[\frac{\Delta Q_{PPn}}{|V_{PPn}|} \right], \quad (10)$$

where $[S]^{-1}$ sensitivity matrix which involves the sensitivity of power plant voltage to reactive power changes in power plant n . Once the pilot nodes are determined, the corresponding power plants with maximum sensitivity of pilot node voltage to reactive power deviations are defined, too.

III. POWER SYSTEM MODELLING

In order to perform the proposed analysis the simplified simulation models of synchronous machines, step-up transformers and transmission lines are used. Synchronous generator is modeled as a first order transfer function from excitation to electromotive force connected behind transient reactance [5]. The static excitation system is modeled as PI regulator of generator terminal voltage, measured after transient reactance, Figure 5. The excitation systems parameters are determined in such a way to get the best fit of the real time reactive power response, recorded at a site. The step-up transformers and short transmission lines are modeled as reactances. The saturation influence is neglected in models used.

Figure 5. The simplified model of synchronous generator with static excitation system

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

The final simulation results of the proposed controller are given for the case study shown in Fig. 1. Only the first operating mode is simulated in order to present the zone controller response.

The first power plant under consideration G_{TENTA} is presented with two generators, the A5 rated 339 MW/367 MVA and the A6 rated 348MW/382MVA. The corresponding step up transformers have leakage reactance of 0.12 pu. The the second power plant G_{TENTB} is also presented with two generator, the B1 rated 620 MW/727MVA and the B2 of the same ratings. The corresponding step up transformers have leakage reactance of 0.065 pu taking the same base power of 367 MVA. Units A6, B1 and B2 have the static excitation with digital implemented AVR and different time responses. Unit A5 has the rotational excitation and therefore it has much slower reactive response than other units. Also, units B1 and A5 are fully loaded while units B2 and A6 are loaded with 70% of rated power.

The simulation is performed in order to demonstrate the ability of the simulated zone controller to maintain the reactive power exchange with surrounding zones at low level under voltage disturbance in neighboring zone.

The simulated disturbance is the voltage deep of 0.05 pu. The voltage dip occurrence in neighboring zone means that that neighboring voltage zone is no more self-sufficient in reactive power. The achieved reactive power responses of different units are shown in Fig. 6. In Fig 7 the Q_{zone_i} change versus time is shown and finally in Fig. 8 the voltage node response is outlined. The initial voltage disturbance occurs at the time of 60 seconds, detail 1 in Fig. 6, Fig. 7 and Fig. 8. After 23 seconds the steady state is detected by CQVC and the correction commands are executed. The reactive power responses are with different time constants (due to different AVR adjustments) and correspond to different levels of active power. So the zone controller reaction occurs after 23 seconds, detail 2 in Fig. 6, Fig. 7 and Fig. 8. It can be seen that the reactive power exchange with neighboring zones is maintained at pre disturbance level with certain error. It is obvious that the zone controller is adjusting the PN voltage in order to decrease the reactive power exchange.

Figure 6. Simulated reactive power responses of units B1, B2, A5 and A6 to close voltage dip, outside of the zone

Figure 7. The Q_{zone_i} change versus time as response to a close voltage dip, outside of the zone

Figure 8. The PN voltage change versus time as response to close voltage dip, outside of the zone

In such way the quasi-independent zonal reactive support is achieved if reactive power demand is within predefined limits. Out of the previously determined reactive limits the CQVC is performing its standard function [3].

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper the quasi-independent zone controller is presented which regulates the total reactive power exchange with neighboring voltage zones. As far as the zone is self-sufficient regarding reactive power needs, the generation is adapted to fit internal zone consumption and the pilot node voltage is adapted appropriately. As soon as limits are reached the import/export of the reactive power out of zone is permitted and voltage support of surrounding zones is available.

The proposed distributed network voltage control based on the network division in quasi-independent voltage-reactive power controlled zones is more robust than centralized control approach because it relies on less informations locally available. The centralized control concept suffers from the certain number of non-confident enough network data and non-calibrated remote measurements, hard to check.

References

- [1] H.Lefebvre, D. Fragnier, J.Y. Boussion, P. Mallet, M. Bulot, "Secondary coordinated voltage control system: feedback of EDF", in Proc. IEEE PES Summer Meeting, Seattle, WA, Jul. 16–20, 2000.
- [2] S. Corsi, M. Pozzi, C. Sabelli, A. Serrani, "The Coordinated Automatic Voltage Control of the Italian Transmission Grid, Part II : Control apparatuses and field performance of the consolidated hierarchical system", *IEEE Trans. on Power Systems*, November 2004, Volume 19, Number 4, pp 1733-1741.
- [3] J. Dragosavac, Z. Janda, J.V. Milanovic, "Coordinated Reactive Power–Voltage Controller for Multi Machine Power Plant," *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, Vol. 27, pp. 1540–1549, August 2012.
- [4] *Network Code on Requirements for Grid Connection Applicable to all Generators (RfG)*, available at www.entsoe.eu
- [5] S. D. Pekarek and E. A. Walters, "An accurate method of neglecting dynamic saliency of synchronous machines in power electronic based systems," *IEEE Trans. Energy Convers.*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 1177–1183, Dec. 1999.